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ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING SPEECH SKILLS OF PRIMARY STUDENTS

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Abstract: The article analyzes the issue of using information technologies to improve English-speaking skills in primary school students, namely the concept, purpose, types and forms, directions, and prospects of their use. The study describes the structure of the modern digital educational environment. It also identifies the capabilities of information and educational technologies in the design and implementation of the educational process, the aspects of their integration at the current stage of educational development, and their alignment with modern requirements. The authors of the study emphasize the educational potential of information technologies.

Key words: information technologies, infocommunication technologies, education, teaching, digital educational environment, speech skills.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilida nutq ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish masalasi – ya'ni, ularning tushunchasi, maqsadi, turlari va shakllari, qo'llanilish yo'nalishlari va istiqbollari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy raqamli ta'lim muhitining tuzilishi tavsiflanadi. Shuningdek, ta'lim jarayonini loyihalash va amalga oshirishda axborot-ta'lim texnologiyalarining imkoniyatlari, ta'lim rivojlanishining hozirgi bosqichida ularni joriy etish jihatlari hamda zamonaviy talablarga muvofiqligi aniqlanadi. Tadqiqot mualliflari axborot texnologiyalarining ta'lim salohiyatini ta'kidlaydilar.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot texnologiyalari, infokommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, ta'lim, o'qitish, raqamli ta'lim muhiti, nutq ko'nikmalari.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется проблема использования информационных технологий для совершенствования навыков говорения на английском языке у учащихся начальных классов, а именно их понятие, цель, виды и формы, направления и перспективы применения. В исследовании описана структура современной цифровой образовательной среды. Выявлены возможности информационных образовательных технологий в проектировании и реализации образовательного процесса, аспекты их внедрения на современном этапе развития образования и соответствия современным требованиям. Авторы исследования подчеркивают образовательный потенциал информационных технологий.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии, инфокоммуникационные технологии, образование, преподавание, цифровая образовательная среда, навыки говорения.

INTRODUCTION

Modern science is developing at an unimaginable speed, spreading its achievements to all spheres of human activity. General informatization is reflected in the field of education through the introduction, adaptation, and dissemination of numerous information technologies at all levels of education—from preschool to university—as well as in additional education. Among the global labor market trends shaping the current education system are freelancing, working outside traditional office or production environments, evolving means of communication between employees, changing tools and methods for managing work processes, interaction between humans and robots or artificial intelligence, accelerated decision-making and data processing technologies, and increased multitasking capabilities. ^[1]

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, educational organizations are still overcoming the traditional challenges of the industrial paradigm of education. Training remains largely focused on individual work, personal assessment systems, pre-designed tasks and datasets, a lack of multitasking, and an emphasis on identifying the single correct solution

to problems. Competency-based training—including future competencies—cannot be developed using outdated educational technologies that were most effective for training industrial-era specialists in the 20th century. Transitioning to a new educational model is only possible through full integration of the educational system into the digital environment. ^[2]

Global changes affecting the modern educational system include the transformation of methods used to deliver educational content, changes in how learners access this content, shifts in the nature of interactions among participants in the educational process, and redefinition of educational content itself. Over recent decades, educational technologies have undergone significant changes, evolving from passive to active formats, from using computers solely for word processing to replacing teachers with robots, integrating modern information technologies, and broadly digitalizing content. Information technology, in a general sense, refers to the processes of accumulating, processing, presenting, and utilizing information through electronic means. ^[3]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, their strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not fully understand the meaning of information but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, English language instruction for elementary school students should not begin with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the very first step of foreign language teaching, it is possible to overload the child and extinguish their interest ^[4]. Thus, teaching a foreign language to young children is a difficult and responsible task. The following methods can be used to teach English to children in a meaningful and interesting way: learning through songs and poems that are difficult to explain or remember in a traditional way; teaching letters or letter combinations to a tune ^[5]; for example, children's learning of the English alphabet through singing is more effective than memorizing it mechanically; games involving mental and physical activities; cartoons: while children may not understand all the words in a cartoon, they try to infer meaning through the actions of the characters. This is an engaging and effective way for children to acquire language skills.

Role playing: when a teacher introduces vocabulary—such as the names of animals or birds—they should use role-play or dramatization. For instance, one student can imitate the howling of a dog or the meowing of a cat, and another student can identify which animal makes the sound ^[6]. There are many other convenient ways to teach English in the elementary grades. Additionally, these methods should be adapted to the individuality and specific abilities of the students. The following methods are widely recognized: games change the learning process both physically and mentally; speaking, listening, and writing games increase students' interest. Multimedia materials, such as video tutorials, animations, and interactive programs, also enhance motivation for language learning ^[7]; students learn to speak through performances, programs, or dialogues, which helps develop speaking skills; practical exercises like simulations and discussions help students apply the language in practical contexts; interactive lessons allow students to learn at their own pace and level of adaptability through computer-based textbooks, online platforms, and applications; music and songs help in learning vocabulary, rhythm, and intonation ^[8]; short stories, illustrated texts, and heroic narratives capture students' interest and expand their vocabulary.

These methods enhance student engagement and comprehension, while also allowing them to express their ideas and absorb new information. It is well known that children are naturally curious. They quickly become bored with repetition. Therefore, it is essential to vary and renew instructional methods. Otherwise, children will anticipate the teacher's strategy and prepare accordingly. Updated teaching methods increase children's enthusiasm ^[9]. How children perform in school and grow up with high aspirations depends significantly on the family environment, community attention, and upbringing in preschool educational institutions ^[10].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The scientific observations and research presented in the article show that 70% of all the information a person receives during their lifetime is acquired during youth, which highlights its importance in the development of a child's personality. It is no coincidence that the knowledge acquired by children at an early age is said to be “set in stone,” as our ancestors used to say. From this point of view, teaching foreign languages to children at an early age leads to the easy acquisition of language skills and abilities. ^[11] Especially if this knowledge, along with skills and abilities, is absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child develops foreign languages as naturally as their mother tongue. Educational games not only help form knowledge, skills, and abilities in a child, but also promote physical health, refresh the mind, boost self-confidence, and assist in forming social relationships with others. ^[12]

In the field of education, information technologies are examined within the context of the term “information and communication technologies” (abbreviated as ICT), since the teacher transmits information through

communication—most often via computer—to the student or pupil. We believe that the concept of “information technology,” in the context of the progressive development of technology, is much broader than the concept of “computer technology,” since computers are not the only tools used in information technology. Modern students use a variety of gadgets (phones, tablets, etc.) and are active on social networks, which can also be adapted for educational purposes.^[13] The fundamental goal of using information technologies in the educational sphere is to improve the quality of education and create effective motivation for students. Through information technology, a teacher can present educational material clearly, create conditions for students to independently search for and obtain information, and monitor their knowledge using computer-based testing. The potential of such technologies is enormous and depends largely on the teacher.^[14]

Thus, the introduction of information technologies into the educational process contributes to the formation of a fundamentally new model of lifelong education, the foundation of which is students' self-analysis of their independent learning activities, supported by modern ICT tools.^[15] In other words, information technologies make the education process continuous—the student learns not only within educational institutions, but also by searching for information, analyzing it, learning about the world, and maintaining communication with teachers and beyond.^[16]

At the current stage of societal development in general—and in education in particular—information technology is not just an auxiliary tool for coordinating the educational process but an integral part of it, with enormous potential. To reiterate, the potential of information technologies in education can be fully realized when the participants of the educational process—both students and teachers—develop appropriate ICT competencies, and when teachers strive to make learning effective and innovative by applying creative and non-traditional approaches.^[17]

CONCLUSION

It should be emphasized that the informatization and digitalization of the education system is a continuous process and an inevitable trend in the development of modern education. Therefore, teachers must adopt and master information technology rather than oppose or reject it. At this stage of educational development, information technology is one of the primary—not auxiliary—methods and forms of instruction, offering significant pedagogical and educational potential.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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